

Extent of Teachers' Participation in Continuous In-Service Training Programmes for Their Improved Job Productivity in Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Akudo, Florence Ukamaka (Ph.D.)

Department of Educational Management and Policy Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State

ABSTRACT: The inefficiencies noticed among many secondary school teachers while performing their teaching responsibilities in the classroom which seems to have negative impact on their job productivity has warranted this present study. Therefore, the present study was designated to find out the extent teachers' participation on continuous in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions guided this study. A descriptive survey research design was employed in the study. Population for this study constituted 5,674 teachers from 258 public secondary schools within the 6 education zones in Anambra State. Sample size for the study consisted of 1,135 teachers from 129 public secondary schools selected at 20% and 50% from both the teachers' population and public secondary schools respectively using the stratified random sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was a researcher-developed 23-item questionnaire titled: "Teachers' Participation in Continuous In-Service Training Programmes and Improved Job Productivity Questionnaire (TPCISTPIJPQ)" and structured on a 4-point scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) in order to answer all the three research questions. The questionnaire was validated by two experts from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one Measurement and Evaluation expert from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State. Reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot-test on a sample 32 teachers from 4 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The scores obtained were measured using Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded coefficient reliability value of 0.75, 0.77 and 0.81 for each cluster respectively, with an overall internal consistency reliability value of 0.78 showcasing that the questionnaire was reliable and dependable to collect the necessary data for the study. Data collated were analyzed using the mean score rated at 2.50 and standard deviation statistics. Findings of the study revealed among others, that the extent of teachers' participation in the various continuous in-service training programmes (on-the-job, off-the-job & computer-based training programmes) for their improved job productivity were all to a low extent. The study recommended among others that secondary school principals in collaboration with Anambra State Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC) should to high extent constantly organize on-the-job continuous in-service training programmes through induction and orientation training programmes, shadowing or co-worker training, job rotation, mentorship from older teachers, internship programmes, school seminars and workshops, coaching and committee assignment for teachers improved job productivity in schools.

KEYWORDS: Continuous, Extent, In-Service Training, Improved, Job Productivity, Participation, Programmes, Teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are one of the most important human resources in the secondary school system. Teachers are the ones that implement the education policy at the classroom level. They stand at the forefront of every student learning. According to Wati (2018), a teacher is a person who helps others to acquire knowledge, competences or values. He or she is a professional with the primary task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, train, assess and evaluate learners in formal education, in primary education and secondary education. The teacher is a figure of the greatest role in determining the quality of learning in an educational institution called school. Teachers are the most important component in the event education of students. As good as any educational programme contained in the curriculum without the role of teachers who cultivate into material that can be understood, it will not mean anything for learners. Teachers therefore, play important role(s) in promoting quality education in the education system (Wati, 2018). These roles besides performing the normal teaching task and promoting students' learning in the classroom as identified by Lauermann (2013) are as follows; providing students with sufficient instructional resources to solve academic problems for positive outcomes,

evaluating and assessing likewise predicting students' grades at the end of the term, supervising students work and monitoring their academic progress in the classroom, providing diverse experiences in school using a holistic approach, prepares high quality, effective, engaging lessons and good lesson plans in order to promote student learning in a classroom, exposing students to new situations and learning experiences, providing an open classroom that encourages questions and involves participation, providing comfortable and supportive atmosphere in the classroom, providing communications and interactions with students and others which may include school administrators, parents and other colleagues, follows the curriculum needs and standards recommended by the State, follows school rules and administrative regulations, instilling students discipline and ensuring their regular attendance to school, among others (Lauermaun, 2013). Teachers through their effective performances and productivity achieves educational goals. It is part of the duty and responsibility of teachers to ensure that educational goals and objectives are actualized. Therefore, the responsibilities of teachers in any education system are enormous. For teachers' efficiency and effectiveness in the education system which leads to high productivity and goal accomplishment, teachers must continually undergo continuous in-service training and retraining programmes. The above statement suggests such contexts that provide teachers with training opportunities for their personal and professional growth and improvement, as well as development of personal characteristics that are related to more optimistic expectations or high productivity (Lauermaun, 2013).

In-service training programmes according to Umoeshiet (2021), are instructional packages designed to improve the efficiency and professionalism of teachers. Thus, in-service training programme includes all those educational courses and activities in which a serving teacher may participate in for the purpose of expanding his or her professional development. UNESCO (2019) described in-service training programmes as the process by which teachers engage in further education or training to refresh or upgrade their professional knowledge, skills and practices in the course of their employment. Mohd (2014) averred that in-service training programme is a professional and personal educational activity designed to improve teachers' efficiency, ability, knowledge and motivation. In-service training programmes are improvement mechanisms used to promote educators work rate, eliminate differences within the professional background of educators, keep the teaching profession abreast of new knowledge, and facilitate educators to tackle responsibilities associated with the changing learning environment (Osamwonyi, 2016). Examples of these in-service training programmes as indicated by Amadi (2013), Ezugoh (2017), Osamwonyi, (2016), Udofia and Ikpe (2012), Umoeshiet (2021) and others, include conferences, workshops, shadowing, seminars, staff meetings, institutes, ICT training, virtual workplace, telematics for teacher training (T3), EduNet, TINTIN, visits and demonstrations, guided practice, coaching, induction and orientation, vestibule training, observations, guidance, university education, committee, professional reading, individual conferences, correspondence courses, exhibitions, among others. All the above in-service training programmes can also be classified under on-the-job and off-the job training programmes. According to Ezugoh (2017), on-the-job training, is training provided during the regular performance of duties. This can take a variety of forms which includes: guidance, shadowing, observations, coaching at the workplace, job mentoring, job rotation, computer-based training at the workplace, among others. Off-the-job training programmes is training provided away from the employee's usual work environment. Off the job training may be in the same building or off site. This training may be provided by trainers working for the same employer as the employees being trained or an outside company hired by the employer. Off the job training is often used to support the employees studying for a formal qualification or exam. In contrast to coaching this type of training usually focuses on knowledge and not skills. Therefore, the benefits of employee development and training include the following: uncover employee potential; enables staff to understand the latest developments and trends within the organization; less confrontations; leads to increased productivity; provides you, the owner or manager of the company, with some insight into the expectations that your employees might have; and remind your work force what your goals are and how you want to drive the desired results (Ezugoh, 2017; Simmons, 2012). Examples of these off-the-job training take the form of conferences, workshops and seminars scheduled away from employees' workplace, vestibule training, apprenticeship, among others (Nnadi, Uzokwe, Helen & Oguzie, 2020). The importance of teachers in-service training programmes cannot be overemphasized. In-service training programmes enable educators to acquire innovative instructional skills to provide rich learning experiences for students in the classroom (Umoeshiet, 2021). In this sense, Ekpoh, Oswald and Victoria in Mohd (2014) posited that, in-service training programmes are organized to increase the performance levels of teachers in the course of discharging their professional duties.

In-service training programmes are deficiency corrective platforms used to bridge the gap between the practice and theory of the teaching profession. The strategic purposes of in-service training programmes include updating educators with modern and

effective pedagogical strategies and equipping them with effective classroom methodologies capable of improving students' academic success. The end-point of in-service training programmes as stated by Akhter, Ali and Nasee (2011) which is aimed at facilitating the professional development and capacity building of classroom teachers. Professional development is a deliberate exercise aimed at increasing the overall competence and quality of teachers. In their views, Gokce (2010) and Oztaskin (2010) submitted that in-service training programme improves educators' professional development in the following areas; teacher professional knowledge, school-based curriculum development, self-development, program adaptation, project-based applications, guidance on student development, development of social consciousness, communication skills and instructional applications of information and communication technologies. This implies that, in-service training programme improves teachers' professional development by exposing them to current instructional process and assessment techniques essential. In a nutshell, when teachers failed to engage in teacher's professional knowledge, they will lack the professional readiness to handle the challenges and complexities of the teaching and learning process (Umoeshiet, 2021). In order to help teachers to keep up with the changing trends and standards of the society and world, they must appreciate the importance of continuous in-service training programmes. Again, through teachers' regular participation in continuous in-service training and retraining programmes, improved productivity is enhanced. Productivity in the words of Eze (2016) and Vipinosa (2015) is the result of the efforts exerted and the resources utilized. Productivity can be measured as a ratio of output to input (Soari in Ajayi & Afolabi, 2012). Within the context of school system, teacher productivity is measured in terms of both efficiency and effectiveness, since the realization of goals and objectives in the school depends on the efficiency and effectiveness of the teachers (Ajayi & Afolabi 2012). Improved teacher productivity is therefore determined from students' academic progress and learning outcomes, that is, from students' assessments and improved test scores, teaching effectiveness which in turn affects students' performance, from analysis of the teacher portfolio which includes teacher lesson plans and notes, student work samples, schedules, videos of classroom interactions, students' grade level, content areas, or specific subject matter and notes from parents, among others. Chikwado and Nwuba (2021) asserted in their study that the teacher improved productivity is observable through their quality services and effective job performance in terms of knowledge of subject matter, classroom management, application of effective teaching methods or techniques and evaluation of student's work, high students' academic performances and achievements, among others. Notwithstanding, the importance of teacher productivity, in Anambra State, the incidence of students' poor academic performances coupled with students' increased failure in both internal and external examinations have raised a lot of questions on the factors which could affect teacher productivity.

For researchers such as Ayeni and Jajua (2021), a failure in teacher quality, effectiveness and productivity can result to undesirable consequences such as poor academic performance of learners, inadequate teaching and learning, and poor achievement of educational goals and instructional objectives in secondary schools. Chikwado and Nwuba (2021) gave a remark that in Anambra State, the Post Primary School Services Commission employs both professional teachers and non-professional teachers. Most of the professional teachers have not received any other form of training after the initial pre-service training. The non-professionals have never received any form of training in the art of teaching, neither were they properly inducted into the school system. Thus making them ill prepared for the task of imparting knowledge. Brennen (2011) asserted that new teachers are faced with several challenges upon beginning their teaching career; such as: class assignment, classroom discipline and management, demanding teaching loads with assignment of extra duties, motivating students, dealing with individual differences among students, assessing students and so on. Hence the need to provide effective in-service or staff development programmes which will assist novice teachers as they begin their teaching career. Subscribing to this view, Mohammed (2016) noted that many teachers after graduation have little or no opportunity for re-training and their training ends as soon as they graduate with no opportunity for updating their knowledge and skills by attending seminars, workshops and conferences that will subsequently enhance their knowledge and skills and their classroom teaching. This therefore emphasizes the importance and the need for every staff (both old & new) including teachers to be constantly and continuously renewed, upgraded and updated in his or her knowledge to be refreshed and to keep abreast with the rapid changing society through staff development programmes (Chikwado & Nwuba, 2021). However, Eze (2016) indicated that teacher productivity seems to be a nagging issue in education. Several researchers like Eze (2016), Ajayi and Afolabi (2012) pointed to the low productivity of teachers. This low productivity could be attributed to many factors and could also have adverse effects on students' performance which is one of the outcomes of teacher productivity. The changing trends and new challenges within the field of education including those in Anambra State has become more frequent and challenging in recent times than ever before. For teachers to remain relevant in service delivery likewise for their improved productivity in the face of these changes and

challenges in the education system, their training and retraining as observed by Eze (2016) must be pursued with renewed vigour. This is because educational concepts and teaching methodologies keep on changing with time. These changes impact both educational delivery, educational goals and outcomes. It is however upon this background that the present study sought to determine extent teachers' participation on continuous in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The extent of development of the secondary education system couple with the provision of quality education for attainment of educational goals is highly dependent on the teachers' productivity. Highly qualified and effective teachers are considered essential for students' high academic performance. But in recent times, the dwindling level of students' academic performance coupled with students' low achievements prevailing in both internal and external examinations in secondary schools all over the country and Anambra State inclusive as observed in a study by Ayeni and Jajua (2021) raises a growing concern about the teacher quality and effectiveness by most education stakeholders in the State. Nevertheless, the issue concerning poor teacher quality is usually visible in their poor productivity. When the teacher productivity is poor, then, this affect students' academic performance, therefore, for improved teacher productivity, this equally warrant laying more emphasis on their continuous active participation and engagement in in-service training programmes. It has been observed that a desirable learning situation is one that is devoid of a prevalent low academic performance of the students. The students will be provided quality instruction which is not characterized with failures attributed mainly to inadequacies in teachers' quality coupled with their limited professional experience and poor productivity. Where there is a prevalence of poor teachers' productivity, there will be factors that impede the quality of instructional tasks delivery in schools and thereby causing low level of students' academic performance. Thus, the need for teachers' continuous in-service training programmes for improved productivity which has created a gap for the present study to fill. Most essentially, continuous in-service training programmes in the form of on-the-job, off-the-job and computer training programmes conducted for teachers act as a catalyst for their effectiveness and productiveness. These programmes serve as great potent means of updating teachers' skills and knowledge for improving instruction and learning. The problem of this present study therefore, is to find out the extent teachers' participation in on-the-job, off-the-job and computer-based continuous in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study was to find out extent teachers' participation on continuous in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, this study ascertained the following:

1. Extent of the teachers' participation in continuous on-the-job in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Extent of the teachers' participation in continuous off-the-job in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Extent of the teachers' participation in continuous computer-based in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the extent of teachers' participation in continuous on-the-job in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the extent of teachers' participation in continuous off-the-job in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the extent of teachers' participation in continuous computer-based in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Quite a number of previous empirical studies and scholarly literature has been written and carried out on staff in-service training programmes. According to Ekpoh, Edet and Nkama in (2013) continuing staff in-service and development programmes for teachers is about reinforcing all the dimensions of good teaching throughout a teachers' career. It is a means of increasing the competence level of teachers in a way that would enable them to contribute to a knowledge base that would in turn also contribute to development of teaching as a profession. The study by Oluwakemi (2011) cited in Ayeni and Jajua (2021) further added to the need for teachers to acquire more knowledge through in-service training such as seminars, conferences and regular workshops during their service. The report expresses that such opportunities be best ways to improve the competencies of teachers and bring about greater achievement of success in students' academic performance. Ayeni and Jajua (2021) study on teachers' quality and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District of Ondo State, Nigeria discovered that teachers' qualifications and teaching experience were adequate while limited opportunities were available for teachers' capacity development and could have significant implications on students' academic performance. The study suggested that teachers' capacity development should be improved and more instructional resources be provided to schools. Umoeshiet (2021) in a study disclosed that instructional applications of ICT component of in-service training programme was provided to a very low extent. The study reported that business educators do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent of provision of instructional applications of ICT component of in-service training programme for improving their professional development in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on their years of teaching experience. Perhaps, this could be why e-learning resources are very lowly utilized for instructional delivery in business education programme in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Therefore, the outcome of the Umoeshiet (2021) study disclosed that teacher's professional knowledge component of in-service training programme was provided to a low extent. The study concluded that the low provision of in-service training programme will negatively affect business educators' professional practice and development of core pedagogical competencies required for improving the quality assurance of business education programme in tertiary institutions. Akuegwu, Nwi-ue and Etudor-Eyo (2013) in a similar vein, reported in a study that the provision of teacher's professional knowledge component of in-service training programme for educators was low. The study revealed a very low extent of provision of teacher's professional knowledge component of in-service training programme for business educators in the areas of knowledge of subject matter, knowledge of learning styles and knowledge of designing learning objectives programme while a low extent of provision of knowledge of curricular documents and instructional planning programme was discovered. The low extent of provision of teacher's professional knowledge component of in-service training programme in tertiary institutions can be attributed to poor funding which has been affecting the Nigerian education system over the years. However, the study reported that ethics in teaching and assessment techniques in-service training programmes were provided for business educators to a high extent. The researcher was of the opinion that attendance of academic conferences and gathering of research publications were the avenue at which business educators were provided ethics in teaching and assessment techniques.

In another study, Udofia and Ikpe (2012) which reported that the provision of instructional applications of ICT component of in-service training programme for educators was inadequate for their professional development. The study revealed a very low extent of provision of instructional applications of ICT component of in-service training programme for business educators in the use electronic mail to share instructional content, use of mobile learning to assess students learning outcomes, use of social networking tools to engage students, use of interactive whiteboards to present subject content, use of electronic bulletin boards to explain subject matter, use of internet telephony for discussing ideas with students and use of podcast to facilitate students' learning experience while the use of power-point in classroom instructions was provided to a low extent. These revelations are in line with the discovery of Donkor and Banki (2017) who reported that educators have a very low in-service training access on ICTs for instructional purposes. Ofojebe and Chukwuma (2015) study on utilization of continuous professional development – CPD for academic staff effectiveness in the higher education sector in contemporary Nigeria. The study also examined the benefits of CPD to academic staff, major areas for academic staff CPD, extent to which academic staff attend CPD and challenges/factors hindering effective utilization of continuous professional development (CPD) for academic staff effectiveness in the higher education sector. The findings of this study revealed that academic staff attendance to both off-the-job and on-the-job training programmes were to a low extent. A study was conducted by Seyed, Hashemi and Ali (2014) on ways to enhance the effectiveness of the mechanisms of in-service courses on Lamerd job performance of teachers in fundamental transformation plan. The aim of this study was to investigate ways of improving the effectiveness of the mechanisms in-service courses for Lamerd teacher's job performance in the

fundamental transformation plan in the 2013-2014 years. Findings of the study revealed that the proposed technology facilities such as computer projectors should be used in classrooms; in-service teachers training and traditional classroom methods and teamwork through workshop be regularly organized for teachers. Ezugoh (2017) also found out in her study on motivational strategies provided for educators for facilitating learning in adult literacy centres in Delta State that is, in-service training programmes were not appropriately provided for educators for facilitating learning in adult literacy centres in Delta State. Ekpoh, Edet and Nkama in (2013) conducted a study on staff development programmes and secondary school teachers' job performance in Uyo Metropolis, Nigeria and found out that teachers who participated in staff development programmes were more effective in their job performance than those who did not, in terms of knowledge of subject matter, classroom management, teaching methods and evaluation of student's work. Nnadi, Uzokwe and Oguzie (2020) study on counsellors' participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria confirmed counsellors' participation in on-the-job and off-the-job in-service training programmes was low.

The finding further revealed that low participation of counsellors in on-the-job in-service training programmes orientation/induction training programmes, seminars organized by the principals for counsellors in school through guest talk, mentoring of newly employed counsellors by the old experienced ones, workshops organized by the school authorities and training through observation. There was low participation of counsellors in the following off-the-job in-service training programmes as computer-based training programmes organized outside the school, conferences organized by the Counselling Association, conferences organized in the university for counsellors, outside workshops, coaching by an expert and apprenticeship or internship programmes for counsellors. The findings of Manafa and Manafa (2020) study showed that teachers were not often involved in training and professional development in their schools. The study further discovered that teachers were not involved in quality training, in-service training, information and communication technology training, orientation for new teachers, classroom instruction-led-training, refresher courses and skills training. All the above previous studies have shown that continuous in-service training programmes can impact on teachers' improved job productivity both in and out of the classroom. Given the importance of various in-service training programmes in the career of serving teachers coupled with their professional development, there seem to be no alternative to sustained and continuous in-service training programmes.

METHODS

A descriptive survey research design was employed in the study. The design was adopted in order to collect information from the public secondary school teachers in Anambra State to sought their opinions concerning the present study. Nworgu (2015) opined that this design involved collecting information from a sample of a population using a research instrument like the questionnaire and thereafter scores are collated and analyzed in order to form inferences and generalization based on the findings. Population for this study constituted 5,674 teachers from 258 public secondary schools within the 6 education zones in Anambra State (Source: Anambra State Post Primary Schools Service Commission - PPSSC, 2021). Sample size for the study consisted of 1,135 teachers from 129 public secondary schools selected at 20% and 50% from both the teachers' population and public secondary schools respectively using the stratified random sampling technique. The sample was drawn at 20% of the teachers' population and 50% of the public secondary school population in Anambra State. In selecting the sample, both the teachers and their public secondary schools were stratified based on the geographical location of the 6 education zones and then, the sample was randomly drawn. Justification for the choice of 20% and 50% for the sample is in accordance with Nworgu (2015) who stated that samples between 5% and 80% are sizeable enough for a study with large population. This was therefore considered in selecting the samples for the study. Instrument for data collection was a researcher-developed 23-item questionnaire titled: "Teachers' Participation in Continuous In-Service Training Programmes and Improved Job Productivity Questionnaire (TPCISTPIJPQ)" and structured on a 4-point scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) in order to answer all the three research questions.

The questionnaire was validated by two experts from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one Measurement and Evaluation expert from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State who determined the face and content validity of the research instrument. Reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot-test carried out on a sample 32 teachers from 4 public secondary schools in Anambra State. These four schools were not included in the study but were only used for the pilot test. The scores obtained after the test were measured using Cronbach Alpha statistics

which yielded coefficient reliability value of 0.75, 0.77 and 0.81 for each cluster respectively, with an overall internal consistency reliability value of 0.78 showcasing that the questionnaire was reliable and dependable to collect the necessary data for the study. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the teachers on a personal and face to face contact to them using the help of six research assistants who were familiar with the education zones and the various public secondary schools selected for the sample in the study. These six research assistants were communicated about the essence of the study and told what to do in order to retrieve the necessary information from the respondents. Distribution of all copies of the questionnaire took a period of one week. Although, a total number of 1,135 copies of the questionnaire distributed but not all the copies of the questionnaire were returned and the reason was that most teachers failed to fill and submit their questionnaire immediately on-the-spot. Most of them took it home and forgot them. This making it 1,025 copies of the questionnaire that were gathered at a 90.3% rate of return and sent for appropriate data analysis. Data collated were analyzed using the mean score rated at 2.50 and standard deviation statistics. The decision rule for taking decision was that any mean score which rated at 2.50 and above was regarded as high extent; meanwhile any of the mean score which rated at 2.49 and below was seen as low extent.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the extent of teachers’ participation in continuous on-the-job in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean Scores and SD Ratings of Teachers concerning Extent of the Teachers’ Participation in Continuous On-The-Job In-Service Training Programmes for their Improved Job Productivity in Secondary Schools in Anambra State
N = 1, 025

S/N	Please indicate the extent of your participation in the under listed on-the-job in-service training programmes. Continuous participation in:	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	X	SD	Decision
1.	Induction and orientation training programmes	108	236	339	342	2.11	0.99	Low Extent
2.	Shadowing or co-worker training	121	190	435	279	2.15	0.51	Low Extent
3.	Job rotation	164	239	318	304	2.26	0.52	Low Extent
4.	Mentorship from older teachers	111	319	352	243	2.29	0.42	Low Extent
5.	Internship programme in school	135	217	346	327	2.16	0.39	Low Extent
6.	Seminars including workshops organized in school	222	303	261	239	2.50	0.52	Low Extent
7.	Staff meetings	440	354	131	100	3.11	0.47	High Extent
8.	Coaching at the workplace	215	206	344	260	2.37	0.60	Low Extent
9.	Committee assignment	109	219	333	364	2.00	0.78	Low Extent
Overall Mean Score =						2.33	0.89	Low Extent

Analysis of data in Table 1 revealed all the items from 1 to 6, 8 and 9 were rated below 2.50 of the accepted mean score by the teachers in order to show their disagreements with all these statements. Except for only item 7 which was rated above 2.50 of the accepted mean score by the teachers in order to show their agreement with the statement. The overall mean score and standard deviation (SD) of 2.33 and 0.89 showcased closeness in the mean responses of the teachers. Therefore, this result indicates that the extent of teachers’ participation in continuous on-the-job in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State was to a low extent.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of teachers’ participation in continuous off-the-job in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean Scores and SD Ratings of Teachers concerning Extent of the Teachers’ Participation in Continuous Off-The-Job In-Service Training Programmes for their Improved Job Productivity in Secondary Schools in Anambra State
N = 1, 025

S/N	Please indicate the extent of your participation in the under listed off-the-job in-service training programmes. Continuous participation in:	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	X	SD	Decision
10.	Individual conferences held outside the workplace	201	239	299	286	2.35	1.08	Low Extent
11.	Seminars together with workshops organized in other locations	214	216	305	290	2.35	1.10	Low Extent
12.	University education higher degree programme	248	297	210	270	2.51	1.12	High Extent
13.	Vestibule training	155	279	304	287	2.29	1.03	Low Extent
14.	Programmed instructions	183	218	317	307	2.27	1.07	Low Extent
15.	Public lectures	175	273	230	347	2.27	1.10	Low Extent
16.	Correspondence training courses	164	159	377	325	2.16	1.04	Low Extent
Overall Mean Score =						2.31	1.09	Low Extent

Analysis of data in Table 2 revealed all the items from 10, 11 and 13 to 16 were rated below 2.50 of the accepted mean score by the teachers in order to show their disagreements with all these statements. Except for only item 12 which was rated above 2.50 of the accepted mean score by the teachers in order to show their agreement with the statement. The overall mean score and standard deviation (SD) of 2.31 and 1.09 showcased closeness in the mean responses of the teachers. Therefore, this result indicates that the extent of teachers’ participation in continuous off-the-job in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State was to a low extent.

Research Question 3: What is the extent of teachers’ participation in continuous computer-based in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Mean Scores and SD Ratings of Teachers concerning Extent of the Teachers’ Participation in Continuous Computer-Based In-Service Training Programmes for their Improved Job Productivity in Secondary Schools in Anambra State
N = 1, 025

S/N	Please indicate the extent of your participation in the under listed computer-based in-service training programmes. Continuous participation in:	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	X	SD	Decision
17.	Microsoft Office Suite application training programmes in Microsoft Excel or Spreadsheet, Outlook, Word processing, PowerPoint, Microsoft OneNote, Microsoft outlook, Microsoft publisher, Microsoft Access, etc	115	203	364	343	2.09	0.99	Low Extent
18.	Basic training programme for beginners related to use of different computer hardware such laptops, desktop, whiteboard, screen touch, digital cameras, graphic tablets, modems, printers, scanners, photocopiers, fax machine, LCD projectors, filmstrip, 3D projectors, etc	103	245	279	398	2.05	1.01	Low Extent
19.	e-learning training programmes in areas such as Internet based learning like videoconferencing, use of google apps like the google classroom and social media application e.g zoom, skype, YouTube, cloud computing, web networking such as like World Wide Web, web browser, among others	88	124	391	422	1.88	0.93	Low Extent

20.	Computer-related storage devices training (disks, CDs, USB drives, zip disks, DVDs, etc.)	104	234	396	291	2.15	0.95	Low Extent
21.	Self-paced computer training courses on videos, CDs or DVDs	170	253	303	299	2.29	1.06	Low Extent
22.	Online tutorials	166	236	345	278	2.28	1.03	Low Extent
23.	Computer software graphic design applications training such as Corel draw, desktop publishing, Adobe page maker coupled with any other 3D graphic design	93	153	414	365	1.97	0.93	Low Extent
Overall Mean Score =						2.10	1.00	Low Extent

Analysis of data in Table 3 revealed all the items from 17 to 23 were rated below 2.50 of the accepted mean score by the teachers in order to show their disagreements with all these statements. None of the items was rated above 2.50 of the accepted mean score by the teachers in order to show their agreement with the statement. The overall mean score and standard deviation (SD) of 2.10 and 1.00 showcased closeness in the mean responses of the teachers. Therefore, this result indicates that the extent of teachers' participation in continuous computer-based in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State was to a low extent.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the study generally revealed that the extent of teachers' participation in the various continuous in-service training programmes (that is, on-the-job, off-the-job & computer-based training programmes) for their improved job productivity were all to a low extent. The finding indicated that the extent of teachers' participation in continuous on-the-job in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State was to a low extent. This finding included that the extent of teachers' participation in such continuous on-the-job in-service training programmes as: induction and orientation training programmes, shadowing or co-worker training, job rotation, mentorship from older teachers, internship programme in school, seminars including workshops organized in school, coaching at the workplace, and committee assignment; were all to a low extent. This finding further indicated that the extent of teachers' participation in staff meetings was to a high extent. This is because it was mandatory that all the teachers were present during staff meetings which was not enough to train teachers in their specific job areas. Rather staff meetings held for teachers were usually for settlement of dispute among teachers and other matters. However, the finding on teachers' low participation in majority of the on-the-job in-service training programmes corroborates with Ayeni and Jajua (2021) study on teachers' quality and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District of Ondo State, Nigeria found out that limited opportunities were available for teachers' capacity development and could have significant implications on students' academic performance. Ezugoh (2017) found out in her study on motivational strategies provided for educators for facilitating learning in adult literacy centres in Delta State that on-the-job in-service training programmes were not appropriately provided for educators for facilitating learning in adult literacy centres in Delta State. Nnadi, Uzokwe and Oguzie (2020) study likewise revealed low extent of teachers' participation in off-the-job training programmes.

The outcome of the finding of Umoeshiet (2021) study disclosed that teacher's professional knowledge component of in-service training programme was provided to a low extent. The study concluded that the low provision of in-service training programme had negatively affected business educators' professional practice and development of core pedagogical competencies required for improving the quality assurance of business education programme in tertiary institutions. Akuegwu, Nwi-ue and Etudor-Eyo (2013) found out that the provision of teacher's professional knowledge component of in-service training programme for educators was low. The study revealed a very low extent of provision of teacher's professional knowledge component of in-service training programme for business educators in the areas of knowledge of subject matter, knowledge of learning styles and knowledge of designing learning objectives programme while a low extent of provision of knowledge of curricular documents and instructional planning programme was discovered. The findings of Ofojebe and Chukwuma (2015) study on utilization of continuous professional development – CPD for academic staff effectiveness in the higher education sector in contemporary Nigeria confirmed that academic staff attendance to on-the-job training programmes were to a low extent.

It was found out that the extent of teachers' participation in continuous off-the-job in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State was to a low extent. This finding included that teachers' continuous participation in individual conferences held outside the workplace, seminars together with workshops organized in other locations, vestibule training, programmed instructions, public lectures and correspondence training courses; were all to a low extent. However, the finding also showcased that the extent of teachers' participation in University education higher degree programmes was to a high extent. This is so because teachers engage into the university education programmes as a result to obtain higher degrees and qualifications. The finding on teachers' low participation in many of the off-the-job continuous in-service training programmes is equally in consonance and does not deviate from the finding of Ofojebe and Chukwuma (2015) study on utilization of continuous professional development – CPD for academic staff effectiveness in the higher education sector in contemporary Nigeria which found out that academic staff attendance to off-the-job training programmes were to a low extent. The finding of Ezugoh's study (2017) indicated that off-the-job in-service training programmes were not appropriately provided for educators for facilitating learning in adult literacy centres in Delta State. The present study finding also agrees with Ekpoh, Edet and Nkama (2013) study on staff development programmes and secondary school teachers' job performance in Uyo Metropolis, Nigeria which found out that teachers who participated in staff development programmes were more effective in their job performance than those who did not, in terms of knowledge of subject matter, classroom management, teaching methods and evaluation of student's work. Nnadi, Uzokwe and Oguzie (2020) study on counsellors' participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria confirmed counsellors' participation in off-the-job in-service training programmes was low.

The finding further revealed that low participation of counsellors in on-the-job in-service training programmes orientation/induction training programmes, seminars organized by the principals for counsellors in school through guest talk, mentoring of newly employed counsellors by the old experienced ones, workshops organized by the school authorities and training through observation. There was low participation of counsellors in the following off-the-job in-service training programmes as computer-based training programmes organized outside the school, conferences organized by the Counselling Association, conferences organized in the university for counsellors, outside workshops, coaching by an expert and apprenticeship or internship programmes for counsellors. The findings of Manafa and Manafa (2020) study showed that teachers were not often involved in training and professional development in their schools. The study further discovered that teachers were not involved in quality training, in-service training, information and communication technology training, orientation for new teachers, classroom instruction-led-training, refresher courses and skills training.

The finding of this present study further revealed that the extent of teachers' participation in continuous computer-based in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity in secondary schools in Anambra State was to a low extent. This finding included that the extent of teachers' participation in Microsoft Office Suite application training programmes in Microsoft Excel or Spreadsheet, Outlook, Word processing, PowerPoint, Microsoft OneNote, Microsoft outlook, Microsoft publisher, Microsoft Access; basic computer training programme for beginners related to use of different computer hardware such laptops, desktop, whiteboard, screen touch, digital cameras, graphic tablets, modems, printers, scanners, photocopiers, fax machine, LCD projectors, filmstrip, and 3D projectors; e-learning training programmes in areas such as Internet based learning like videoconferencing, use of google apps like the google classroom and social media application e.g zoom, skype, YouTube, cloud computing, web networking such as like World Wide Web, web browser, among others; computer-related storage devices training (disks, CDs, USB drives, zip disks, DVDs, etc.); self-paced computer training courses on videos, CDs or DVDs; online tutorials; and computer software graphic design applications training such as Corel draw, desktop publishing, Adobe page maker coupled with any other 3D graphic design; were all to a low extent. This finding is in line and does not deviate from the finding of Seyed, Hashemi and Ali (2014) study on ways to enhance the effectiveness of the mechanisms of in-service courses on Lamerd job performance of teachers in fundamental transformation plan, which revealed that the proposed technology facilities nick Electrical training such as computer projectors should be used in classrooms; in-service teachers training and traditional classroom methods and teamwork through workshop be regularly organized for teachers. Umoeshiet (2021) study discovered that instructional applications of ICT component of in-service training programme was provided to a very low extent. The study reported that business educators do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent of provision of instructional applications of ICT component of in-service training programme for improving their professional development in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on their years of teaching experience. Perhaps,

this could have been the reason why e-learning resources were very lowly utilized for instructional delivery in business education programme in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

The finding also agrees with Udofia and Ikpe (2012) study which found out that the provision of instructional applications of ICT component of in-service training programme for educators was inadequate for their professional development. The study revealed a very low extent of provision of instructional applications of ICT component of in-service training programme for business educators in the use electronic mail to share instructional content, use of mobile learning to assess students learning outcomes, use of social networking tools to engage students, use of interactive whiteboards to present subject content, use of electronic bulletin boards to explain subject matter, use of internet telephony for discussing ideas with students and use of podcast to facilitate students' learning experience while the use of power-point in classroom instructions was provided to a low extent. These revelations are in line with the discovery of Donkor and Banki (2017) who reported that educators have a very low in-service training access on ICTs for instructional purposes. All the findings of the present study have shown that continuous in-service training programmes can impact on teachers' improved job productivity both in and out of the classroom. Therefore, based on the findings of this present study which reported low extent of teachers' participation in all the continuous in-service training programmes would have been responsible for teachers' inefficiencies, poor performance which had negative influence on their improved productivity.

CONCLUSION

Teachers' active participation in continuous in-service training and retraining programmes is beneficial to both their professional development and school effectiveness. This process assists teachers to continually update their knowledge and upgrade their skills for good performances which leads to improved job productivity. Notwithstanding the benefits of the continuous in-service training programmes, yet many teachers cease to actively engage into many of these programmes for improvement in their job productivity, just as discovered in the present study. This study however, establishes and concludes that the extent of teachers' participation in the various on-the-job, off-the-job and computer-based continuous in-service training programmes for their improved job productivity were all to a low extent. For improved teacher productivity in schools together with school effectiveness which will foster positive outcomes, adequate concern must be given to teachers' participation in continuous in-service training programmes. Hence, the need for the under listed recommended proffered below.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this present study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Secondary school principals in collaboration with Anambra State Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC) should to high extent constantly organize on-the-job continuous in-service training programmes through induction and orientation training programmes, shadowing or co-worker training, job rotation, mentorship from older teachers, internship programmes, school seminars and workshops, coaching and committee assignment for teachers improved job productivity in schools.
2. Anambra State government should encourage and support teachers' active participation in off-the-job continuous in-service training programmes such as individual conferences, seminars and workshops, vestibule training, programmed instructions, public lectures and correspondence training courses to a high extent, through the provision of adequate financial assistance and scholarships for teachers improved job productivity in schools.
3. Anambra State government in collaboration with PPSSC, school heads -principals and the private sector should frequently organize computer-based in-service training programmes for teachers to a high extent in all areas of Microsoft Office Suite application training programmes, basic computer training programme for beginners, e-learning training programmes, among others, for their improved job productivity in schools. This also calls for the State government effective implementation of ICT policy which will support continuous training of teachers through utilization of the ICT tools and facilities provided in schools.

REFERENCES

1. Ajayi, I.A. & Afolabi C.Y. (2012). The influence of sex and experience on secondary school teachers' productivity in South West Nigeria. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 4 (3).
2. Akhter, S.H., Ali, S.W., & Nasee D.M. (2011). A critical analysis of the existing status of the in-service training of teachers at secondary level in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 3 (6), 417-420.

3. Akuegwu, B.A., Nwi-ue, F.D., & Etudor-Eyo, E. (2013). Lecturers' participation in capacity building programmes in South-South Nigeria: Implications for sustainable development. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*, 4 (2), 279-292.
4. Amadi, N.M. (2013). *In-service training and professional development of teachers in Nigeria: Through open and distance education*. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED567172.pdf>.
5. Ayeni, A.J. & Jajua, M.A. (2021). Teachers' quality and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District of Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Liberal Arts and Humanities (JLAH)*, 2 (4), 19-32. Retrieved from <https://jlahnet.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/3-1.pdf>.
6. Brennen, A.M. (2011). *Comprehensive paper on staff development*. Retrieved from <http://www.soencouragement.org/comprehensive-paper-on-staff-development.htm>.
7. Chikwado, A. & Nwuba, C.P. (2021). Influence of staff development programmes and secondary school teachers' job performance in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 4 (2), 176 – 184.
8. Donkor, A.K., & Banki, R.D. (2017). Assessing the impact of in-service training programmes on basic school teachers of Chiana in the Kassena Nankana West District of Ghana. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 6 (4), 64 – 76.
9. Ekpoh, U.I., Edet, A.O. & Nkama, V.I. (2013). Staff development programmes and secondary school teachers' job performance in Uyo Metropolis, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4 (12), 217-222. Retrieved from <http://www.iiste.org/>.
10. Eze, T.A.Y. (2016). Teachers' perception of the impact of training and retraining on teachers' productivity in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Business and Management*, 4 (3), 33-37.
11. Ezugoh, T.C. (2017). Motivational strategies provided for educators for facilitating learning in adult literacy centres in Delta State. *Unpublished Master's degree thesis*. Submitted to the Department of Adult and Continuing Education, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
12. Gokce, A.T. (2010). Alternatively certified elementary school teachers in Turkey. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2, 1064 -1074.
13. Lauermaun, F.V. (2013). Teacher responsibility: Its meaning, measure, and educational implications. Retrieved from <https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/>.
14. Manafa, I.F. & Manafa, J.E. (2020). Developing human resources in secondary schools in Anambra State for sustainable development in teaching and learning through continuous teachers training and development. *Global Journal of Education, Humanities and Management Sciences (GOJEHMS)*, 2 (1), 19–29. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342664038>.
15. Mohammed, A. M. (2016). *Creating opportunities for continuing professional development of teachers. The National Teachers' Institute Experience*. Lead paper presented at the 1st National Conference of the Faculty of education, University of Abuja, Abuja, 17-21 October.
16. Mohd, Z.C.O. (2014). The need for in-service training for teachers and its effectiveness in school. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*, 2 (11), 1-9.
17. Nnadi, G.C., Uzokwe, H.E. & Oguzie, A.E. (2020). counsellors' participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Guidance and Counselling Studies*, 4 (1), 133-146. Retrieved from <http://www.jgcsunizik.org/>.
18. Nworgu, B.G. (2015). *Educational research. Basic issues and methodology*. Enugu: University Trust Publishers.
19. Ofojebe, W.N. & Chukwuma, E.T.C. (2015). Utilization of continuous professional development for academic staff effectiveness in the higher education sector in contemporary Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies (JETERAPS)*, 6 (4), 306-314. © Scholarlink Research Institute Journal, jeteraps.scholarlinkresearch.com.
20. Osamwonyi, F.E. (2016). In-service education of teachers: Overview, problems and the way forward. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7 (26), 83–87.
21. Oztaskin, O. B. (2010). Identifying the in-service training needs of the social studies teachers within the context of lifelong learning. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2, 3036-3042.

22. Seyed, A., Hashemi, E.A. & Ali, P. (2014). Ways to enhance the effectiveness of the mechanisms of in-service courses on Lamerd job performance of teachers in fundamental transformation plan. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 4 (1) 333 - 343.
23. Simmons, K. (2012). *The benefits of employee development and training*. Retrieved from <http://www.business2community.com/leadership/the-benefits-of-employee-development-and-training>.
24. Udofia, U.I. & Ikpe, U.N. (2012). Administration of in-service training and teachers' attitude to work in private secondary Schools in Cross River State of Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 2 (10), 305–311.
25. UNESCO (2019). *Teacher policy development guide*. Paris: UNESCO.
26. Umoeshiet, E.A. (2021). Extent of provision of in-service training programmes for improving the professional development of business educators in tertiary institutions in Delta State. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education (NIGJBED)*, 8 (2), 135-145. Retrieved from www.nigjbed.com.ng.
27. Vipinosa, L.D. (2015). Productivity, work values and teaching effectiveness of science teachers in Capiz State University. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary research and development*, 2 (5).
28. Wati, S. (2018). *Definition of teacher*. Retrieved from <https://repository.uir.ac.id/427/2/bab2.pdf>.

Cite this Article: Akudo, Florence Ukamaka (Ph.D.) (2022). Extent of Teachers' Participation in Continuous In-Service Training Programmes for Their Improved Job Productivity in Secondary Schools in Anambra State. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(2), 455-467